

Survey of Radiographer abnormality detection system (RADS) - Ability of Professional & to be radiographers

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ABSTRACT:

Introduction: Radiographer Abnormality Detection System (RADS), involves 'Red Dot System' in which radiographers affixing a red sticker/red-dot/star to a radiograph, highlighting the presence of acute abnormality on radiographs in the emergency settings and communicating to the referring doctor about the identification of that abnormality. However, its use India is limited. The purpose of this study was to investigate the ability and skills of radiographers in SGT Hospital (India) in detecting abnormality on multi-modalities such as X-ray, Mammography, CT Scan, MRI and Ultrasound and additional training is required for radiographers to participate in above mentioned system which may be helpful in emergencies. **Aim:** The aim of this study was to survey the professional radiographers and PG students about Radiographer Abnormality Detection System (RADS) at Shree Guru Gobind Singh Tricentenary (SGT) Medical College, Hospital & Research Institute, Gurugram, Haryana. **Material and Methods:** A survey was conducted, in which a cross-sectional questionnaire form was developed that contained 24 questions and data were collected from 9 professional radiographers and 23 PG students in the department of Radio-Diagnosis and Imaging at SGT Hospital (India). The radiographers include professional radiographers who have completed their diploma or bachelor's degree and are currently working as professional radiographers and post graduate students (to be radiographers) who are pursuing their masters degree and have completed the bachelor's degree in the respective field. Out of all, two radiographers had the qualification of diploma and rest of seven had the degree of bachelor's in the respective department and one amongst them were also pursuing their master's degree simultaneously. The results of this survey were analysed using conventional descriptive statistics of response frequencies, quantitative & comparative analysis and percentage of the sample. **Result:** A filled questionnaire form were received from 32 participants 75% (n=24/32) showed satisfaction that RADS will be beneficial with 96.8% response rate in which 59.3% (n=19/32) were agreed & 37.5% (n=12/32) were strongly agreed that necessary steps should be taken for the implementation of RADS in India, while 25% (n=8/32) did not know about RADS and hence not mentioned any suggestions. **Conclusion:** The study found that information about Radiographer Abnormality Detection (RADS) can play a significant role in providing competent and skilled radiographers in future, who can provide good facilities and serve well to patients. This finding presents that establishment of RADS in India may help them to improve the knowledge with diagnostic proficiency and aid to save patient lives in emergencies. Radiographer commenting acts as a conduit in emergency situations for communication between radiographers and the referring doctor/radiologist as an emergency team. Furthermore, there is a need for implementation of RADS in India as it will provide skilled radiographers beneficial for patients during emergencies and night hours.

Keywords: emergency, patient care, Radiographer Commenting, RADS, red-dot system, health care settings

INTRODUCTION:

A good health care system is the facet of good health. In India, there has been significant improvement in the health care system, but still the health care system is not satisfactory. The condition of the states is yet miserable

in other aspects of health care system, particularly in terms of availability of good specialists and well-trained professionals, and more importantly the quality of patient care services.¹ It has been seen that quality increase on health care system with primary focus on patient care and provided number of skilled health

professionals has improved quality of healthcare system.^{2,3} Government departments are promoting flexible and innovative area of allied health professionals as well as greater inter-professional teamwork.⁴

Talking about the department of Radiology and imaging, the role of radiographers is enhancing in the diagnostic imaging in terms of patient handling or radiation protection management, but role in commenting on diagnostic radiograph is limited because traditionally, the radiographers (or radiologic technologists) are doing the job of production of radiographic images and the interpretation of radiographs has been limited to doctors and radiologists.^{5,6} However, radiographic examination is an essential component of disease diagnosis within many patient pathways. It is not only the radiograph but the communication of an accurate interpretation of the radiograph(s) to the referring doctor at a time appropriate to inform patient management that defines the importance of a radiographic examination.⁶ Radiographers are in good position to counter the pressure in contribution to the image interpretation in emergencies but their role in the emergency department has been limited and they are seen occasionally offering informal opinions regarding acute abnormalities on the radiographs they acquire⁷. The feasibility of employing radiographer's diagnostic knowledge to enhance the overall outcomes of emergency patients has been investigated. In India, where maximum health care setups including hospitals (government or private) or diagnostic centers are lacking night shift radiologists due

to low patient load or economic crises or cost cutting, the radiographer commenting could help in aid to save patient lives in emergencies and night hours via implementing Radiographer Abnormality Detection System (RADS)^{7,8}.

Due to the difference in the demand and availability of radiologists, the health care system gets affected. The unavailability of timely services to patients causes tremendous problems particularly during emergencies and the night shifts. Radiology reporting has been limited in these fields especially in Australia, Europe, and some Asian countries including India. It has been observed that immediate availability of reports is of great importance particularly during emergencies and can be advantageous in saving patients' lives by providing appropriate and timely treatment to patients where RADS can play an important role.⁹

The system involved radiographers affixing a red sticker/red-dot/star to a radiograph, as a 'Visual Cue' so to communicate to the referring doctor that an abnormality has been identified. Affixing red sticker/red-dot/star is referred as "Red Dot System" which was proposed as a multi-team approach to image interpretation within the emergency department widely implemented in UK¹⁰. A paper published in 1985 by Berman et al. is considered the foundation of this system titled "Reducing errors in the accident department: a simple method using radiographers". RADS is also named differently as "red dot", "commenting", "radiographer opinion" and "radiographer image triage"^{11,6}

Transverse process fracture

<https://www.imageinterpretation.co.uk/thoracolumbar.php>

Wiley Online Library

Evaluating the true clinical utility of the red dot system in radiograph interpretation - Brown - 2012 - Journal of Medical Imaging and Radiation Oncology

Adapting this system showed radiographers playing a more meaningful role in the emergency settings. The Red dot/sticker assists the referring doctor/radiologist in the interpretation of radiographs prior to the availability of the radiology report¹². In case the radiologists are unavailable, RADS can be useful in significant findings that have an impact on the patient's treatment.¹³ The purpose of this study was to investigate the ability and skills of radiographers in SGT Hospital (India) in detecting abnormality on multi-modalities such as X-ray, Mammography, CT Scan, MRI and Ultrasound and additional training is required for radiographers to participate in above mentioned system which may be helpful in emergencies.

Lacunae:

Radiographer commenting has potential to improve timely diagnosis and management of patients in emergencies, where delays between image capture and radiological reporting occurs radiographer commenting can act as a conduit for communication between radiographers and the referring doctor. This involves the confidence and ability of radiographers to detect and describe abnormalities on radiographs especially the trauma radiographs. Furthermore, inexperienced junior doctors, staffing emergency departments may be supported by this system.

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

Study Design:

In this study professional radiographers and PG students were included which required a medical imaging/radiography degree or equivalent. The radiographers include professional radiographers who have completed their diploma or bachelor's degree and are currently working as professional radiographers and post graduate students (to be radiographers) who are pursuing their master's degree and have completed the bachelor's degree in the respective field.

A questionnaire form was developed which contained questions related to the benefits of RADS ability of professional radiographers and to be radiographers. The aim of this study is to assess the radiographer's abnormality detection abilities and skills in emergencies.

Participants & Setting:

In this survey, 9 professional radiographers and 23 PG students in the department of Radio-Diagnosis and Imaging at SGT Hospital (India) were included. In this department 20 radiographers are currently working.

Questionnaire content and procedure:

Following a critical review of the literature, a cross-sectional survey was undertaken using a postal

questionnaire; the data collection tool. This approach permitted the collection of data at a specific point in time and facilitated the optimization of the study breadth. A pilot study was also undertaken to ensure the accuracy, appropriateness and relevance of the questionnaire. A questionnaire was designed to be the most efficient way of collecting data; filled and signed by radiographers and PG students posted/ working in the department. Questionnaire contained 24 questions and was filled from 32 participants out of whom 25 were males while 7 were females; 27 were in age range (20-25 years) while 5 were age range between (25-30 years).

The questionnaire was divided into three sections: The first explored the gender, age and clinical experience of the participants, the second asked respondents to provide information about their confidence and ability in detecting an abnormality on various modalities and third section included questions regarding participation in RADS being a mandatory or voluntary. Suggestions were taken from them about the procedure that they had gone through i.e. whether RADS should be implemented in order to be beneficial or not.

The data collected in this survey does not include bachelor students who were on posting in the department or the lateral entry students. Also, the unwilling participants were also excluded (exclusion criteria).

Ethical Consideration:

The investigation was approved by the central ethical committee of the radiology department SGT Medical College, Hospital & Research Institute. Completing the survey implied consent and the participation was voluntary.

Research design:

The current study used a quantitative analysis which is well defined, logically deductive; objective uses numerical data and a comparative analysis to establish the value of independent variables.

The data was collected from the radiographers which included the gender, age, experience, and investigation that the patient had gone through. The questionnaire was filled in a prospective manner and the data has been collected in a proper manner at the department of Radio-Diagnosis & Imaging. The radiographers of all age group, without any discrimination on the basis of sex, castes etc. were included with complete honest and faith to development of the survey.

Data analysis:

The results of this questionnaire were analysed using conventional descriptive statistics including response frequencies and percentages of the participants. To avoid

human error, for the calculation MS excel 2010 version was used.

The purpose of data analysis is to categorize, organize, and summarize the data that have been collected.

RESULTS:

A questionnaire was made which contained 24 questions and filled from 9 professional radiographers and 23 PG students i.e. 32 participants.

Clinical experience:

When participants were asked about their clinical experiences; out of 32 participants 65.6% (n= 21/32) have their experience between 0-2 years; 18.75% (n= 6/32) between 2-5 years; 9.3% (n= 3/32) between 5-7 years and 6.2% (n= 2/32) between 7-9 years of clinical experience.

Awareness about RADS:

Results showed that only 68.7% (n= 22/32) participants were aware about RADS while remaining participants (n= 10/32) don't know about RADS.

Detecting an abnormality in X-Ray:

Participants responded their confidence level in detecting any abnormality in X-Ray as 15.6% (n= 5/32) of the participants marked their confidence level between (0-2); 53.1% (n= 17/32) between (2-5); 18.7% (n= 6/32) between (5-7); and 3.1% (n= 1/32) between (7-9) in detecting an abnormality in X-Ray.

Detecting an abnormality in Mammography:

50% (n= 16/32) of the participants marked their confidence level between (0-2); 31.2% (n= 10/32) between (2-5) and 12.5% (n= 4/32) between (5-7) in detecting an abnormality in Mammography; while two participants did not specify a preference.

Detecting an abnormality in CT Scan:

25% (n= 8/32) of the participants marked their confidence level between (0-2); 46.8% (n= 15/32) between (2-5); 25% (n= 8/32) between (5-7) and 3.1% (n= 1/32) between (7-9) in detecting an abnormality in CT Scan.

Detecting an abnormality in MRI:

46.8% (n= 15/32) of the participants marked their confidence level between (0-2); 34.3% (n= 11/32) marked their confidence level between (2-5); 12.5% (n= 4/32) between (5-7) and 6.2% (n= 2/32) between (7-9) in detecting an abnormality in MRI.

Detecting an abnormality in Ultrasound:

59.3% (n= 19/32) of the participants marked their confidence level between (0-2); 25% (n= 8/32) between

(2-5); 9.3% (n= 3/32) between (5-7), and 3.1% (n= 1/32) between (7-9) in detecting an abnormality in Ultrasound while one participant did not specify a preference.

Education:

Participants were asked if they have ever heard about RADS or do they had the appropriate training received to participate in RADS successfully. Nine of the participants (28.1%) had never heard about RADS while 22 (68.7%) knew about the term.

When asked about their working in the hospitals having establishment of RADS 25% (n= 8/32) of the participants have worked in hospitals that had established RADS and 75% (n= 24/32) have worked in the hospitals that had not. The participants also showed the desirability of receiving image interpretation education where 28.1% (n= 9/32) of the participants marked themselves between (0-2); 37.5% (n= 12/32) between (2-5); 28.1% (n= 9/32) between (5-7); 3.1% (n= 1/32) between (7-9) in rating the desirability of receiving image interpretation education ; while one participant did not specify a preference.

Most of the participants 93.7% (n= 30/32) were also in favor that education about image interpretation should be given at the undergraduate level and one among them (3.1%) was not in favor while one participant does not showed any response.

RADS ability and implementation:

For the necessary steps to be taken for the implementation of RADS, maximum number of participants 96.8% response rate showed desire (59.3% ; n= 19/32 agree & 37.5% ; n= 12/32 strongly agree) that necessary steps should be taken for the implementation of RADS. Only one participant (3.1%) strongly disagreed.

The response about their ability to detect suspected tumor in cross-sectional imaging, 28.1% (n= 9/32) marked themselves between (0-2), 46.8% (n= 15/32) between (2-5) and 21.8% (n= 7/32) between (5-7) in having the ability to detect suspected tumor in cross-sectional imaging; while 1 participant does not showed any response.

In having the ability to detect any fracture in case of trauma, 18.7% (n= 6/32) marked themselves between (0-2); 21.8% (n= 7/32) between (2-5); 31.2% (n= 10/32) between (5-7) and 28.1% (n= 9/32) between (7-9).

In having the ability to detect the abnormality in the radiograph of patient under the treatment 12.5% (n= 4/32) marked themselves between (0-2); 50% (n= 16/32) between (2-5); 31.2% (n= 10/32) between (5-7); and only one (3.1%) between (7-9) while one participant did not attempted the question.

In having the ability to understand the diagnostic report made by the radiologist, only two (6.2%) marked

themselves between (0-2), 34.3% (n= 11/32) between (2-5); 40.6% (n= 13/32) between (5-7) and 18.7% (n= 6/32) marked themselves between (7-9).

Training regarding RADS:

Only 9.3% (n= 3/32) of them had received training regards RADS but none of them were satisfied with the training they had received and were passionate about receiving more training regarding RADS, while rest 90.6% (n= 29/32) participants had not received any training regarding RADS but they mentioned that they were eager to receive training and learn more about RADS. None of our participants had done any online course regarding RADS. The main reason they mentioned was due to the lack of awareness in the Indian Paramedical Staff.

RADS: Beneficial or not:

When asked about their interest whether RADS is beneficial or not, 84.3% response rate (n= 27/32) participants agreed that RADS is beneficial since it will improve the quality of radiography and will also lead to the betterment of the health care settings. While remaining 15% (n= 5/32) of them had no idea whether RADS is beneficial or not.

RADS: Voluntary or Mandatory:

When respondents were asked if they believed that participation in RADS should be voluntary or mandatory within their departments, 28.1% (n= 9/32) of them considered that RADS should be voluntary whilst 56.2% (n= 18/32) participants replied that it should be mandatory, because they think that it will improve the abnormality detection ability of radiographers in the radiology department of the concerned hospital which will be beneficial to patients as well and the remaining 15.6% (n= 5/32) participants did not specify a preference.

While asked how about managing the emergency situations, 78.1% (n= 25/32) agreed with the fact that RADS is helpful in managing the emergency situation for the referring doctor, one participant did not agree whilst five (15.6%) participants did not specify a preference and one out of them was not sure.

Suggestions:

Suggestions given by our participants were as follows:

- It improves the quality of the radiographers.
- It will be helpful in emergency situations
- When radiologists are unavailable. it will aid in saving patients life.
- It should be made a subject and included in their academics.
- Regular training should be conducted for students and workers (radiographers).

DISCUSSION:

The results of this study indicate that better information about Radiographer Abnormality Detection System (RADS) can play significant role in providing competent and skilled radiographers in future who can serve well and provide better care to patients. The participants also showed the desirability of receiving image interpretation education and were interested that regular training should be conducted for students in their academic years and for workers (radiographers). Most of them were in the favor of establishment of RADS to get the better results which help them to improve the knowledge with diagnostic proficiency and aid to save patient's lives in emergencies and especially during night hours when usually Radiologists/ doctors are not available especially in India due to various reasons as mentioned earlier.

This study involved surveying the Ability of Professional Radiographers who are already working in the respective field and to be radiographers who in future, if given proper training, can serve well to patients in emergency situations. The method of survey distribution proved an advantage in the data collection. The participants without RADS in place acknowledged a desire to implement such a system. There are many barriers in the implementation of RADS, some out of which faced by our participants included under this study were lack of knowledge, training & awareness about RADS as no such classes are held regarding it because it is considered that traditionally the job of radiographers is just to obtain images and no interest is shown on radiographers doing commenting or interpretation and if doing so it is considered that they are doing diagnosis which is actually misinterpreted here because it is not the diagnosis and it is just commenting the radiograph that an abnormality is seen in case of emergencies or during the hours especially at night if the radiologists are unavailable so that delay in reports could not occur. The implementation of RADS depends on how to introduce the system. Adapting this system showed radiographers playing a more meaningful role in the emergency department as study done by Andrew Murphy et al. showed involvements of directors/senior officials playing key roles in implementation of RADS as maximum studies recommends its need, nowadays.

The interest of participants showing whether RADS is beneficial or not, 84.3% response rate (n= 27/32) participants agreed that RADS is beneficial since it will improve the quality of radiography and will also lead to the betterment of the health care settings. If this investigation displayed several strengths but it also had the limitations i.e. the small sample size of this study. Furthermore, this study only involves participants from a particular hospital and involves quite a young cohort of respondents. Therefore, the findings of this study may

not necessarily represent the overall use of RADS in India. A further limitation relates to the age of the data as it is now approximately 2 years old.

CONCLUSION:

The results of the present study showed that 75% (n= 24/32) participants are satisfied that RADS will be beneficial while 25% (n= 8/32) participants did not know about RADS and hence not mentioned any suggestions regarding it. The ability and skills of radiographers in SGT Hospital (India) in detecting abnormality on multi-modalities such as X-ray, Mammography, CT Scan, MRI and Ultrasound was assessed and it also showed that maximum number of respondents worked at the hospitals where RADS was not established reason being that no any training, information or awareness was provided and also no any theoretical curriculum was followed in their academic years. The implementation of RADS was highlighted and considered to be a priority for future of health care setting. Study acknowledges radiographers conveying information regarding clinical significance of RADS to be within the scope of practice in India. The implementation of RADS will be more accurate method of communicating potential abnormalities to a referrer. It is seen that adopting this system involves additional training required for to be radiographers, newly qualified radiographers and radiographers already working; to participate in above mentioned system which may ultimately improve patient care in the emergency departments in the health care settings.

Credit Statement/Contribution:

Urooj Mushtaq (1) conception, design of the work, the data acquisition, analysis, and interpretation of the data, Gayoor Fayaz (2) contributed in commenting on the paper, and statistical analysis.

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Conflict of Interest:

No conflict of interest.

Disclosure:

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Ethical approval:

Ethical approval was taken from central institutional committee of SGT Medical College, Hospital & Research Institute, Gurugram, Haryana.

Consent:

Informed consent was obtained from all participants.

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